

A Review On Human Communication Theory And Practice In Media Psychology

Vimala Govindaraju

Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: January 01, 2022</p> <p>Accepted: August 01, 2022</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Theory, Media, Psychology, Human, Communication Practice</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.6949709</p>	<p><i>Media psychology has emerged as a branch of psychology dealing with the interaction between media technology and people. Media psychology is a rapidly evolving field of journalism theory and practice dealing with the description of human behavior conditioned by exposure to the mass media. A study of individual and group media effects and core components of media culture that identify psychological patterns of human attitudes and behaviors in a multicultural media environment. Exploration of psychological phenomena and perceptual mechanisms of media texts. This article aims to provide an overview of the theory and practice of human communication in media psychology.</i></p>

Introduction

Media psychology, the interdisciplinary nature of the field, and the ever-changing way people interact with the media in every aspect of their lives, from work, education, entertainment to social involvement. The goal of media psychologists is to answer these questions by combining an understanding of human behavior, cognition, and emotions with an equivalent understanding of media technology. Today, the media exists in almost every area of life and is an area of research that becomes even more important as the world becomes more interconnected. Unlike some media studies, media psychology does more than just deal with content. Media psychology considers the entire system. Psychology is the key to understanding the impact of technology. The goal of media psychologists is to find answers and solutions by combining an understanding of human behavior, cognition, and emotions.

Media psychology is a new field of psychology that studies how people are affected by mediated communication. Media psychology relies heavily on psychology and communication, but also incorporates science from other disciplines such as sociology, media studies, anthropology, and fan studies. In addition, this discipline is still scattered across many disciplines, and many scholars who do not consider psychology as their primary area of interest are studying the impact of the media on individuals. Scholars pointed out that there is no beginning or end. This is a continuous loop that includes technology developers, content producers, content awareness, and user responses. It should differ from previous studies in that it provides a new approach to understanding and clarifying the theoretical structure of communication.

Motivational theory

Motivation has been defined in different ways over the years, but all of them have one thing in common. It is the power to drive, rejuvenate and direct action. The classic definition of motivation is "an internal process that stimulates, directs, and sustains behavior" (Reeve, 2016). Wright (2016) motivates i) destabilizes the organism, ii) moves the organism in one direction rather than in the other direction, iii) moves it more or less vigorously, and iv) more or less permanently emotionally. Franken (2006) described motivation as "awakening, direction, and sustainability of human behavior." Motivational theory focuses on the behavior of participants or respondents who examine and evaluate behavior or survey responses to monitor behavioral changes and identify the underlying cause of the subject's behavior. In many theories, motivation arises from the so-called evaluation of motivational behavior to perform (the word evaluation is rarely used in connection with motivation, but the process described is emotional. Similar to the process recorded in the literature). Although the theory is usually formulated through research, observations, or experiments comparing groups of participants. The application of motivational theory must be personal and personal, taking into account the cultural and emotional differences of the individual, and the individual institution in choosing the end result or purpose is their own.

Emotion

Emotion is a term used in psychology to describe a conscious and subjective experience characterized by a mental state, biological response, psychological or physiological expression (such as facial expression). Emotions differ from "emotions" in that they subjectively express emotions. In other words, emotions are personal only to the individual. Emotions also differ from "mood" by the duration of their existence. Moods last longer than emotions. Traditionally, emotions as the subject of research from a media psychological point of view are mainly understood in the context of media entertainment research. It deals with the general mechanism of media user participation and emotional tendencies towards characters, as well as the implications of media violence and more specific depictions of horrifying or disturbing material. Emotional psychological studies show that strong emotional events are better remembered than neutral events (Klauer, 2004). From a media perspective, one remembers much more emotional stories (Burke, Heuer, & Reisberg, 1992) and photographs (Safer, Christianson, Autumn, & Österlund, 1998) than neutral stories and photographs. However, some people remember little background information about emotional stories and forget about the surrounding details surrounding the emotional realm of the photo.

The effect of emotional media content on the memory of the program context. Media content also emotionally affects the ability to remember the context of a program. Motivation and emotion include physiological arousal, which is different from a rational and gentle cognitive process (Reeve, 2018). A messages sent within 3 minutes of offensive and stimulating messages are not remembered as well as messages without previously stimulating messages (Lang, Newhagen, & Reeves, 1996; Mundorf, Drew, Zillmann, & Weaver 1990. Scott & Goff, 1988). Also, TV commercials viewed within 3 minutes of erotic ads will not be recalled, as will previously published commercials without erotic ads (Wirth & Lübkemann, 2004). A study of emotional images in news broadcasts found that little information immediately preceding negative emotional images was remembered (Newhagen, 1992). Meanwhile, the author has discovered a visual supportive effect that is presented after a negative emotional image. Valence and the effect of specific emotions on memory. Literature presented so far have examined all emotions in terms of arousal (Levine & Pizarro, 2004). Motivation, along with emotions, is part of a core psychological phenomenon called emotions.

Figure 1: Motivation and What Really Drives Human Behavior

Social Cognitive Theory and Social Perception

Information processing-focused social cognition and perception are combined in shaping the impression of others, and the types of information presented can also make a difference. Since sovereigns are known as social cognition, it has been pointed out in the literature that social cognition and cognition are studies of how individuals build and infer about others 'cognitions (Ansari, 2012). Identifying and utilizing social cues to determine people's characteristics such as social roles, connections, rules, contexts, or credibility is called social cognition. Social knowledge related to understanding social roles, norms and expectations is also assigned to this category. Social situations and interactions are surrounded by schemas. They add information from appearance, voice, intonation, facial expressions, and nonverbal communication to the database. Individuals can perform their activities effectively by observing successful display of behavior (Bandura, 1989). Internal or

external reactions to a person's behavior that affect the likelihood that the behavior will continue or stop are called enhancements. Extensions can be good or bad, self-starting, or found in your environment. It is related to the construction of social cognitive theory, as it is most related to the interaction and cognition between behavior and the environment. Observations are raw data of social cognition based on three-way interactions between people, events, and behaviors. These sources are used to support one's perceptions and conclusions about others.

Literature showed social cognitive theory used to explain and analyze the relationships between personal, behavioural, and environmental impacts and reach the goal of helping students achieve a high degree of self-adjusting learning (Vimala, 2021). Scholar also pointed this theory is a multifaceted causal structure in which the belief in self-efficacy works according to recognized goals, expectations of results, and recognized environmental hazards and facilitators in regulating human motivation, behaviour, and well-being. In social cognitive theory, beliefs about effectiveness serve as one of many determinants of motivation, emotion, and behaviour. In social cognitive theory, values-based recognized goals provide additional self-incentives and guidelines for healthy behaviour (Bandura, 1986).

Models of Human Memory and Recall

Memory refers to the spiritual process of encoding, storing, and retrieving environmental information. Human cognition includes many closely related mental processes such as perception, attention, memory, and thinking. An important and central cognitive process is memory, which is generally associated with the storage and memory of environmental information. An interesting topic in memory research is how to improve memory performance and memorize information. The process of building new memory is called coding. The next step is storage to keep information up to date. Finally, searching is the process of accessing previously stored knowledge. Recalls are active rebuilding processes, not incidents, facts, ideas, or replicas of process memory. Each time you access the memory for retrieval, the memory changes, which re-encodes the memory. The positive effect is that recalls improve future retention.

Human memory is generally divided into short-term memory and long-term memory. The model proposed by War and Norman retained the concept of primary and secondary memory originally proposed by William James. Their model has been regarded as the first behavioral model of memory because it quantifies the properties of primary memory (Atkinson & Shiffrin, 1968). Previous work on memory has been fully expanded to lead to one of the influential models of the human memory system proposed by Atkinson and Shiffrin (Sternberg & Sternberg, 2009). In their model, memory consists of three structures. Sensory register memory, short-term memory and long-term memory. Environmental stimuli first enter the sensory register. This memory can store a large amount of information, but the information is only stored for a very short time. Information that requires attention is then transferred to short-term storage. As a result of different types of control processes, information is transferred to long-term storage for more persistent storage. B. Maintenance and widespread repetition, heuristics, or other storage strategies are important to be able to transfer information from short-term storage to long-term storage.

The memory process is considered to be continuous from the superficial sensory process to the deeper semantic memory process. The process of shallow memory involves a basic and superficial analysis of information, such as the physical and sensory properties of information. Caching requires some detection and labeling, and deeper processing involves higher levels of analysis, such as processing the meaning of information and connecting with existing memory traces. Deeper levels of analysis are expected to contribute to more sustainable and longer memory capacity. In other words, the information is stored in long-term memory as a result of the amount of analysis and processing performed on the environmental inputs. Therefore, for better memorization of stimuli, it is important that environmentally available stimuli can activate attention and be incorporated into control processes or deeper levels of processing. Previous studies have shown that color is one of the variables that has this potential. Color can affect attention levels and can later trigger emotional arousal that contributes to control processes that improve memory capacity (Farley & Grant, 1976; Pan, 2010; Pan, 2009; Eysenck, 2014; MacKay & Ahmetzanov, 2005).

Figure 2: Types of Memory.

Attitudes and Attribution

Attitude is defined as a reaction towards something or someone. Attribution theory is most commonly associated with social psychology. It dominated the work reported in the journal of social psychology and replaced cognitive dissonance theory as an important conceptual framework in this field (Fiancham, 1983). In its broadest concept, attribution theory is characterized as a study of how people reach the answer to the "why" question. (Kelly, 1972a). Attribution theory is best described as a study of perceived causality. (Fiancham, 1983). The nature of attribution and explanation, in common sense, deals with "why the event happened". Then explain the event by explaining the cause of the event (Jaspars&Fincham, 1983). Attribution theory identifies the nature of the expectation factor, and further, attribution theory can show how the accompanying explanation is indirectly related to behavior in a particular situation (Jaspars&Fincham, 1983).

The literature, which also points to the attribution of intention and disposition, has been widely considered to be the second major influence on the emergence of attribution theory. A typical process-oriented attribution theory was developed by someone who explicitly addressed the problem of causal attribution of events and behaviors (Kelley, 1972). These three classical attribution theorists above have specified the underlying processes of various attribution content, each ignoring the distinction between causality and responsibility (Shultz &Schleifer, 1983). Attribution theory is most commonly associated with social psychology. Nevertheless, attribution theory is beginning to influence areas of psychology that are not traditionally associated with this approach. According to Jaspars and Fincham (1983), attribution theory has become a major study of social psychology. This theory has led most of the previous two-page advertising research (Crowley & Hoyer, 1994). In advertising and marketing, consumers can either attribute their complaints to the advertiser's intention to sell the product (one-way advertising) or communicate honestly with the consumer about the characteristics of the product or service (two-way advertising) (Crowley & Hoyer, 1994). The inclusion of negative information, especially the importance of negative messages, is not normative, so recipients of the information will believe that the advertiser or speaker is honest and telling the truth (Crowley & Hoyer, 1994). By including negative information, consumers will believe that advertisers are telling the truth, not just trying to sell their products (Eisend, 2007).

According to Crowley and Hoyer (1994), attribution theory provides an explanation for the increased credibility provided by two-way messages, but determining the effectiveness of two-way messages in relation to attitudes towards advertising and brands. Is very limited. In addition, attribution theory does not provide guidance on the structure of the message structure, except that it needs to include negative attributes (Crowley & Hoyer, 1994), but the number of negative messages that need to be mentioned in the ad. Is not specified in this theory. In a broader sense, attribution theory seems to be limited and narrow-focused, beyond the research it has produced. Therefore, current research was conducted to rethink the basic beliefs of attribution theory and how they apply to the study of messaging over the Internet.

The Attribution Theory

In psychology, attribution is the judgment we make about the cause of the behavior of others. Attribution theory describes these attribution processes used to understand why an event or behavior occurred. Attribution theory presupposes that people try to determine why people do what they do, that is, attributes cause behavior. In one person was forced to perform an action that requires one to determine whether another person believes in one (Weiner, 1974). He identified ability, effort, difficulty of work, and luck as the most important factors influencing the attribution of achievement. Attributions are categorized according to three causal relationships: locus of control, stability, and controllability. There are two poles in the locus of control dimension: the locus of control inside and outside. The dimension of stability captures whether it causes a change over time. For

example, ability can be categorized as a stable internal cause and effort can be categorized as an unstable internal cause. Controllability distinguishes between controllable causes such as skills or performances and uncontrollable causes as aptitude, mood, behavior of others, and luck. Attribution theory deals with how individuals interpret events and how they relate to their thoughts and actions. Heider (1958) first proposed the psychological theory of attribution, while Weiner and colleagues (Jones et al., 1972; Weiner, 1974, 1986) with an important research paradigm in social psychology. Attribution theory presupposes that people try to determine why people do what they do, that is, attributes cause behavior. Anyone who wants to understand why someone else has done something can attribute one or more causes to that action.

Fundamental attribution is a three-step process (1) the behavior must be perceived or observed, (2) the behavior must be believed to have been intentional, and (3) whether the behavior is perceived. Others believe that the person was forced to act (in this case, the cause is due to the situation) or not (in this case, the cause is due to another person). Scholar focused and identified on achieving his theory of attribution in ability, effort, difficulty of work, and luck as the most important factors influencing the attribution of achievement (Weiner, 1974). Attributions are categorized according to three causal relationships: locus of control, stability, and controllability. The dimension of stability captures whether it causes a change over time. For example, ability can be categorized as a stable internal cause and effort can be categorized as an unstable internal cause. Weiner (1980) stated Attribution theory has been used to explain the difference in motivation between high achievers and achievers. Attribution theory believes that success comes from reliable high skills and effort, so high achievers work on success-related tasks rather than avoiding them. Failure is believed to have been caused by bad luck or bad testing. Therefore, failure does not affect their self-esteem, but success builds pride and self-confidence.

The Elaboration Likelihood Theory

The most popular theory of persuasion at the time, the theory of persuasive elaboration, was based on learning principles and regarded persuasion as a function of attention, understanding, acceptance, and retention of persuasive communication (Hovland, Janis, and Kelley, 1953). As the number of persuasive studies began to grow, many inconsistencies appeared in the results. For example, increasing the same variables as number of discussions, source expertise, use of fear can be more convincing in one experiment, less persuasive in another, and one-third more effective. In addition, many theories of attitude change have been developed to explain the various processes by which persuasion can occur, but each theory seems to predict persuasion only under certain conditions. The Elaboration Likelihood Model (Petty and Cacioppo, 1986) was developed to explain previous contradictions in attitude studies. While previous models tended to emphasize the effects of specific variables and the processes by which they occurred, elaboration likelihood theory organized multiple two-way persuasion processes for attitude changes. The central path includes the changes that occur when people consider the presented topic-related information relatively thoughtfully. In contrast, the peripheral pathways of persuasion involve processes that require relatively little thought about relevant information. Instead, attitudes are modified by simple associative processes (such as classical conditioning) or the use of various mental shortcuts and heuristics. By noting that variables affect attitudes differently at various points along the elaboration likelihood, the elaboration likelihood theory can explain seemingly contradictory findings in the persuasive literature.

Figure 3: Persuasion Routes

Central Route Processing

Elaboration likelihood theory organizes the process of attitude change into two pathways to persuasion: the central and peripheral pathways. The central path to persuasion is to carefully consider the relationship between the information associated with the attitude object and the relevant knowledge stored in memory. Careful

consideration of the topic-related information presented involves generating positive and / or negative thoughts about the position taken. In the central route, the valence of these thoughts (positive or negative) is related to the direction of belief, the thoughts are new, more positive or negative than before, and to some extent determine the magnitude of attitude change. Thoughts about messages form an important element that links internal knowledge to the information presented in the message. The more confident people are in the thoughts they generate in the central route, the more they determine a person's attitude (Petty, Briñol, and Tormala, 2002). The focus of thinking under the central route is often the perceived desirability of the results in communication and the perceived possibility that those results occur (Petty and Wegener, 1991; Ajzen and Fishbein, 2000). The motivation for a person to think about a message discussion is the perceived personal relevance of the message and whether he or she enjoys thinking in general. can be affected by many variables (Petty and Cacioppo, 1979b; Cacioppo, Petty, and Morris, 1983). A person's thinking ability is the level of distraction in the context of belief and the number of times a message is repeated (Petty, Wells, and Brock, 1976; Cacioppo and Klein, 1979). When a person is motivated and able to reflect the relevant information presented, the end result of this careful process is clearly expressed, accessible, confidently retained, and integrated into the person's overall belief structure. (Petty and Cacioppo, 1986).

Peripheral Route Processing

In everyday life, one of the motivations or abilities to carefully consider all possible compelling communications along the path of the central route is often lacking. Nonetheless, many persuasion processes require little or no consideration of substantive information, which can lead to attitude changes. In elaboration likelihood theory, such processes are placed in peripheral routes and include simple clues available in the context of beliefs and reliance on spiritual shortcuts called heuristics. The context of belief can evoke emotional states (such as happiness) associated with the position advocated through classical conditioning (Staats and Staats, 1958). Rather than carefully considering the substantive discussion, he decided that "experts are generally correct" (Chaiken, 1987). Another common method used when either motivation or skill is lacking is to simply count the number of discussions presented, rather than assessing their benefits (Petty and Cacioppo, 1984). Persuasion routes do not require careful consideration of the content of the message, but they can effectively lead to persuasion, at least in the short term. For the sake of explanation, it was convenient to split the persuasion process into two different paths.

However, according to the Elaboration Likelihood Theory, persuasion is based on the elaboration likelihood. Continuities are from processes that do not require thinking, such as subliminal classical conditioning that occur out of consciousness, to processes that require some effort, such as counting discussions and drawing conclusions based on one's influence. It extends to processes that require careful thinking. Pros and cons for making important life decisions. Along much of the continuum, both peripheral and central processes can occur and affect attitudes at the same time (Petty, 1994). However, as the likelihood of refinement increases, the central routing process careful evaluation of problem-related information tends to dominate the attitude to more peripheral processes (such as heuristic reliance). The distinction between the central route and the peripheral route is the nature of the information itself (Petty, Wheeler, Bizer, 1999).

Implications

In terms of practical implications, this article portrayed a greater outlook and elaboration on the theoretical trends of human communication theory and practice in media psychology. The implication of media psychology is rapidly evolving field of journalism theory and practice, the subject of which is the description of human behavior conditioned by exposure to the mass media. A study of individual and group media effects and core components of media culture that identify psychological patterns of human attitudes and behaviors in a multicultural media environment. Exploration of media psychological phenomena and perceptual mechanisms of media, manipulation in the media, and optimizing knowledge about a person's mental abilities.

Directions for Future Study

Even so, this body of literature still needs to be further expanded and explicated by including publications from high impact journals. However, it should be noted that theoretical foundations and rigorousness need to be further solidified for future scholarly endeavours. More fundamental and theoretically motivated research is needed to further explain the human communication theory issues in the country. Theory based research can yield more knowledgeable insights, direction and progression of theoretical application and development in media psychology research.

Conclusion

This literature review has identified, to varying degrees, many theories classified as relational or structural, capturing the complexity of media psychology and human communication. The approved theories include the relatively important role of context, knowledge and intervention in the use of media in daily work. The literature

on these theories is particularly applicable to the psychological environment of the media and enriches existing knowledge and understanding of human communication theory and practice. It provides a general perspective on the theoretical and practical reasons that human attitudes towards communication can represent.

Acknowledgments

Author would like to share her research knowledge via publishing article and the cost bared by her own.

Authors' Contributions

Dr Vimala Author for this article based from Human Communication background. Her field of expertise was on interpersonal communication since her doctoral dissertation focused on Interpersonal Communication skills in doctors and patients' communication. Currently, the author shared her literature review experience in the combination of Human communication theory in media psychology perspective.

References

- Ajzen, I., & Fishbein, M. (2000). Attitudes and the attitude-behavior relation: Reasoned and automatic processes. *European review of social psychology*, 11(1), 1-33.
- Ansari, A. M. (2012). *The politics of nationalism in modern Iran* (Vol. 40). Cambridge University Press.
- Atkinson, R. C., & Shiffrin, R. M. (1968). Human memory: A proposed system and its control processes. In *Psychology of learning and motivation* (Vol. 2, pp. 89-195). Academic Press.
- Bandura, A. (1989). Human agency in social cognitive theory. *American psychologist*, 44(9), 1175.
- Burke, A., Heuer, F., & Reisberg, D. (1992). Remembering emotional events. *Memory & cognition*, 20(3), 277-290.
- Cacioppo, J. T., & Petty, R. E. (1979). Effects of message repetition and position on cognitive response, recall, and persuasion. *Journal of personality and Social Psychology*, 37(1).
- Cacioppo, J. T., Petty, R. E., & Morris, K. J. (1983). Effects of need for cognition on message evaluation, recall, and persuasion. *Journal of personality and social psychology*, 45(4).
- Chaiken, S. (1987). The heuristic model of persuasion. In *Social influence: the ontario symposium* (Vol. 5, pp. 3-39).
- Crowley, A. E., & Hoyer, W. D. (1994). An integrative framework for understanding two-sided persuasion. *Journal of Consumer research*, 20(4), 561-574.
- Daley, D. M. (1998). Attribution theory and the glass ceiling: Career development among federal employees. *International Journal of Organization Theory & Behavior*.
- Eisend, M. (2007). Understanding two-sided persuasion: An empirical assessment of theoretical approaches. *Psychology & Marketing*, 24(7), 615-640.
- Fincham, F. D. (1983). Developmental dimensions of attribution theory. New York, NY: Academic Press, Inc., 117-162.
- Fincham, F. D., & Jaspars, J. M. (1983). A subjective probability approach to responsibility attribution. *British Journal of Social Psychology*, 22(2), 145-161.
- Franken, R. (2006). *Human motivation* (6th ed.). Florence, KY: Wadsworth.
- Harvey, J.H. & Weary, G. (1985). *Attribution: Basic Issues and Applications*, Academic Press, San Diego.
- Heider, F. (1958). Perceiving the other person. *The psychology of interpersonal relations.*, 20.
- Hovland, C. I., Janis, I. L., & Kelley, H. H. (1953). Communication and persuasion.
- Jones, E. E. (1972). *Attribution: Perceiving the causes of behavior*. Morristown, NJ: General Learning Press.
- Kelley, H. H. (1972). Causal schemata and the attribution process? n EE Jones, DE Kanouse, HH Kelley, RE Nisbett, S. Valins, & B. Weiner (Eds.), *Attribution: Perceiving the causes of behavior*: 151-174. Morristown.
- Klauer, K. C., & Zhao, Z. (2004). Double dissociations in visual and spatial short-term memory. *Journal of experimental psychology: General*, 133(3), 355.
- Lang, A., Newhagen, J., & Reeves, B. (1996). Negative video as structure: Emotion, attention, capacity, and memory. *Journal of Broadcasting & Electronic Media*, 40(4), 460-477.
- Levine, L. J., & Pizarro, D. A. (2004). Emotion and memory research: A grumpy overview. *Social cognition*, 22(5: Special issue), 530-554.
- Lewis, F. M., & Daltroy, L. H. (1990). How causal explanations influence health behavior: Attribution theory. In Glanz, K., Lewis, F.M. and Rimer, B.K. (eds.) *Health Education and Health Behavior: Theory, Research, and Practice*. San Francisco, CA: Jossey-Bass Publishers, Inc.
- Newhagen, J. E., & Reeves, B. (1992). The evening's bad news: Effects of compelling negative television news images on memory. *Journal of communication*, 42(2), 25-41.
- Petty, R. E., & Cacioppo, J. T. (1979). Effects of forwarning of persuasive intent and involvement on cognitive responses and persuasion. *Personality and Social Psychology Bulletin*, 5(2), 173-176.

- Petty, R. E., & Cacioppo, J. T. (1979). Issue involvement can increase or decrease persuasion by enhancing message-relevant cognitive responses. *Journal of personality and social psychology*, 37(10), 1915.
- Petty, R. E., & Cacioppo, J. T. (1984). Source factors and the elaboration likelihood model of persuasion. *ACR North American Advances*.
- Petty, R. E., & Cacioppo, J. T. (1986). The elaboration likelihood model of persuasion. In *Communication and persuasion* (pp. 1-24). Springer, New York, NY.
- Petty, R. E., & Cacioppo, J. T. (1986). The elaboration likelihood model of persuasion. In *Communication and persuasion* (pp. 1-24). Springer, New York, NY.
- Petty, R. E., & Wegener, D. T. (2014). Thought systems, argument quality, and persuasion. In *The content, structure, and operation of thought systems* (pp. 155-170). Psychology Press.
- Petty, R. E., Brinol, P., & Tormala, Z. L. (2002). Thought confidence as a determinant of persuasion: the self-validation hypothesis. *Journal of personality and social psychology*, 82(5), 722.
- Petty, R. E., Wells, G. L., & Brock, T. C. (1976). Distraction can enhance or reduce yielding to propaganda: Thought disruption versus effort justification. *Journal of Personality and social Psychology*, 34(5), 874.
- Petty, R. E., Wheeler, S. C., & Bizer, G. Y. (2000). Attitude functions and persuasion: An elaboration likelihood approach to matched versus mismatched messages. *Why we evaluate: Functions of attitudes*, 133-162.
- Reeve, J. (2016). A grand theory of motivation: Why not? *Motivation and Emotion*, 40(1), 31-35.
- Reeve, J. (2018). *Understanding motivation and emotion*. John Wiley & Sons.
- Safer, M. A., Christianson, S. Å., Autry, M. W., & Österlund, K. (1998). Tunnel memory for traumatic events. *Applied Cognitive Psychology: The Official Journal of the Society for Applied Research in Memory and Cognition*, 12(2), 99-117.
- Schleifer, M., Shultz, T. R., & Lefebvre-Pinard, M. (1983). Children's judgements of causality, responsibility and punishment in cases of harm due to omission. *British Journal of Developmental Psychology*, 1(1), 87-97.
- Staats, A. W., & Staats, C. K. (1958). Attitudes established by classical conditioning. *The Journal of Abnormal and Social Psychology*, 57(1), 37.
- Sternberg, R. J., & Sternberg, K. (2009). *Cognitive Psychology* (5th ed.). Belmont, California, USA: Wadsworth, Cengage Learning.
- Vimala, G. (2021) A Review of Social Cognitive Theory from The Perspective of Interpersonal Communication. *Multicultural Education*, 7 (12). pp. 488-492.
- Weiner, B. (1974). *Achievement motivation and attribution theory*. Morristown, N.J.: General Learning Press.
- Weiner, B. (1980). Attribution theory and human motivation. *New York: Holt, Reinhart & Winston. Winograd, K. (2003). The functions of teacher emotions: The good, the bad, and the ugly. Teachers College.*
- Weiner, B. (2012). *An attributional theory of motivation and emotion*. Springer Science & Business Media.
- Wirth, W., & Lübckemann, M. (2004). Jenseits plumper Nacktheit. In *Fernsehwerbung—quo vadis?* (pp. 137-167). VS Verlag für Sozialwissenschaften.

Author Information

Dr Vimala Govindaraju
Lecturer
Faculty of Language and Communication,
University Malaysia Sarawak, Malaysia
